

Supplementary materials: Segmentation-based tracking of macrophages in 2D+time microscopy movies inside a living animal

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Figure S 1: Top: Histogram in the presence of the small spot noise having bright image intensity. The blue bars inside the red square indicate the noise. The number of pixels of the noise N_{noise} is obtained by summing the counts inside the red square. In this histogram, $N_{\text{noise}} = 9$. Bottom: After the histogram crop, the image intensity of the noise is changed to I_{\min} to consider the noise as the background. The number of counts for $I_{\text{new};\text{max}}$ is increased by 9 as shown in the blue bar denoted by the red arrow.

Figure S 2: Schematic picture of the space discretization. Here, $u_{i,j,k}$ denotes the value of the unknown function u at a pixel position (i, j) in k^{th} time slice. In a clockwise direction, the values of u at corners, $u_{i,j,k}^{1,1}$, $u_{i,j,k}^{1,-1}$, $u_{i,j,k}^{-1,-1}$, and $u_{i,j,k}^{-1,1}$, are defined. The gradients, $\nabla^{1,0}$, $\nabla^{0,-1}$, $\nabla^{-1,0}$, and $\nabla^{0,1}$, are computed at the center of edges.

Comparison with other local thresholding techniques

The different local threshold methods, “Berssen” [1], “Hybrid of Niblack and Berssen” [1–3], “Sauvola” [4], and “White” [5], are applied to the images filtered by space-time filtering. To obtain the optimal parameters for each method, we perform the same approach for the parameter optimization presented in Appendix A. We follow the notations of the parameters for each local thresholding technique given in the article [3] and the values of parameters used for the optimization are as follows: $w = \{10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80\}$, $k = \{-0.2, -0.15, -0.1, -0.05, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2\}$, $R = \{15, 45, 75, 105, 128, 150, 180, 210\}$, $\text{bias} = \{0.35, 0.4, 0.45, 0.5, 0.55, 0.6, 0.65, 0.7\}$, $T_c = \{10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45\}$. The obtained optimal parameters of each method are shown in Table S 1. Then, the SUBSURF method is applied to the thresholded images to measure the performance of segmentation. Here, the parameters of space-time filtering and the SUBSURF method are the same as the ones described in Appendix A. Figures S 3, S 4, and Table S 2 show the performance for two macrophages (“i” and “ii” in Section 3.1) by measuring the mean Hausdorff distance, IoU index, and Sørensen–Dice coefficient. In these results, the proposed method and “White”+SUBSURF show higher performance than other methods. Figure S 5 illustrates the differences between the local Otsu’s method and “White” in detail. The images obtained after the application of the “White” method contain more background noise than the ones obtained by the local Otsu’s method (second and third rows). The SUBSURF method can remove such noise, e.g., in case $\theta = 0$, however, sometimes the noise still remains e.g., when $\theta = 48$ and $\theta = 134$ as shown in the last row of Figure S 5.

	w	k	R	bias	T_c
Berssen	30				30
Niblack & Berssen	10	-0.15			30
Sauvola	80	-0.2	210		
White	80			0.7	

Table S 1: Optimal parameters used in segmentation methods.

Figure S 3: The quantitative comparison for the macrophage denoted by “i” in Fig. 9. **a**: The mean Hausdorff distance from the gold standard, **b**: IoU (Jaccard) index, **c**: Sørensen–Dice coefficient. Time sequence in the horizontal axis indicates the order of time frames, and its interval is 4 minutes.

Figure S 4: The quantitative comparison for the macrophage denoted by “ii” in Fig. 9. **a**: The mean Hausdorff distance from the gold standard, **b**: IoU (Jaccard) index, **c**: Sørensen–Dice coefficient. Time sequence in the horizontal axis indicates the order of time frames, and its interval is 2 minutes.

	“i”			“ii”		
	$\overline{d_H}$	\overline{IoU}	\overline{DSC}	$\overline{d_H}$	\overline{IoU}	\overline{DSC}
Proposed	1.65	0.77	0.86	1.19	0.80	0.89
Bernsen	7.61	0.57	0.70	3.65	0.62	0.22
Niblack & Bernsen	12.5	0.42	0.58	10.25	0.43	0.60
Sauvola	22.3	0.35	0.49	31.9	0.44	0.60
White	1.46	0.84	0.91	1.34	0.82	0.90

Table S 2: The average over time of the mean Hausdorff distance $\overline{d_H}$, the average over time of IoU (Jaccard) index \overline{IoU} , and the average over time of Sørensen–Dice coefficient \overline{DSC} obtained by using five segmentation methods.

Figure S 5: Original (top row) and segmented images (second–fifth row) at $\theta = 0$, $\theta = 48$, and $\theta = 134$ obtained by different methods.

References

- [1] John Bernsen. Dynamic thresholding of gray-level images. In *ICPR '86: International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, 1986.
- [2] Wayne Niblack. *An introduction to digital image processing*. Strandberg Publishing Company, 1985.
- [3] Anna Korzynska, Lukasz Roszkowiak, Carlos Lopez, Ramon Bosch, Lukasz Witkowski, and Marylene Lejeune. Validation of various adaptive threshold methods of segmentation applied to follicular lymphoma digital images stained with 3, 3'-diaminobenzidine&haematoxylin. *Diagnostic Pathology*, 8(1):1–21, 2013.
- [4] Jaakko Sauvola and Matti Pietikäinen. Adaptive document image binarization. *Pattern Recognition*, 33(2):225–236, 2000.
- [5] James M White and Gene D Rohrer. Image thresholding for optical character recognition and other applications requiring character image extraction. *IBM Journal of Research and Development*, 27(4):400–411, 1983.